

THE USAGE AND METHODS OF NEW INFORMATION
TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

In developing society, our country requires learning skills that could help it keep pace with the development of science and technology. Educational systems in a community and consequently education will not be able to separate from other social institutions, national and international interactions widely known in the global village. Education in the twenty-first century is the center from which all changes and developments arise. Information technology in education needs a culture. This culture needs to be learned along with the use of hardware resources. The system needs to be educated to use information technology; otherwise, purchase and transfer of technology and investment will be nothing but wasting resources. Although these technologies are not impartial in any sense they should be used as means for communicating information, in the existing social structures. However since the process of change and transformation is in the nature of human social institutions, the educational system is also prone to some alterations. But the fundamental problem is that what strategies should be adopted so that education systems in developing countries do not only follow developed countries but grow and progress base on their own needs in the path of progress. In this paper, after explanation about the role of information technology and its place in education in underdeveloped countries and Iran, a discussion is presented on how to enter the field of information society and how to use information technologies.

INTRODUCTION. Today, our society, our entire way of life, is so developed and intensified that it can even be viewed as an invisible phenomenon. The role of information and communication technologies, which are rapidly entering our lives, is becoming more and more important not only in manufacturing or other fields, but also in the education system. As the President of our country Sh.Mirziyoev noted, "Today, the movement in the modern

information space is so intense that it is so far from now that it happened so far away that it cannot be ignored that it has nothing to do with us.

It is certainly possible that hundreds of years of development of such a nation or nation is lagging behind "(Mirziyoev Sh. 2017). Information and communication technologies are not new to anyone at the moment, but the fact that it is constantly improving shows new aspects. As the society is renewed, certain changes and turns occur in every area of the society. This can be explained by the contrast between the previous education system and the current educational system. Therefore, the role of information and communication technologies in the education system is very important. Today knowledge and information are the main keys of obtaining the productivity, competition, wealth and comfort. So countries have concentrated on approaches for increasing the gaining of better-quality education. In order to develop the human capital, it is necessary to look at our schools and education and see if our education is progressing in step with the world that is changing and developing quickly. The problem is that if we compare the modern world with the last-century, we are confronted with dazzling developments of sciences, business, medical services, communications and many other fields. But visiting the schools, we, surprisingly, see no difference between the contemporary classrooms and the last-century ones; students sitting in rows, holding pencil and paper, noting down hurriedly what the teacher is saying and writing so that they know them by heart and give them back at the time of test quickly. This is while many matters have been changed through the sciences and technical development, but education and the students learning methods and the teachers.

The use of Information Technology in the classroom has left behind the traditional methods of giving long boring lectures. Using IT the teachers can create interesting audio and visual presentations which will keep the students engaged and will give them a greater understanding of all the concepts. Besides this, such a methodology can give rise to interactive sessions between students and teachers. Everyone likes watching animated videos. Using Information Technology the whole classroom can be digitalized thus making both teaching and the process of learning much easier. Today various informational and communicational technologies have the ability of facilitating the education and learning process. Also there is an evidence stating that information technologies provide effective and inflexible methods for professionally developing teachers. Information Technology has given rise to various tools and applications which can be used by school administration and teachers to track the progress of individual students and the parents can also be kept up to date about the achievement of their child. This technology can also be useful for the teachers to help the students in their weak subjects and provide them some extra time and notes. Thus IT has saved the teachers from old methods of maintaining student records on books and registers. There are given the majorities of Information technologies in Education.

- Technology helps students to stay motivated during the learning process. Most students don't like to go to school if they feel like they are wasting their time. When there is technology allowed in the classroom, then teachers have an opportunity to let kids work at a pace which suits them the best without disturbing others. They can look up additional information about a subject they are learning about that day, play educational games that reinforce the lesson, or work on advanced material Because many of today's technology options allow students to see

how well they are doing compared to the average of all users, it gives them a chance to push harder for themselves and their education. Many of the programs that encourage learning also issue rewards or award certificates, which helps to make the lessons fun as well.

- It encourages more communication between teachers and parents. When there is technology in the classroom, then there are more opportunities for parents and teachers to connect with each other. Using a blog for the classroom can help parents get to see what their children are learning each day.

There are options for chat boxes, instant messaging, and other forms of communication as well.

- It creates new ways to learn for today's student. There are three critical forms of intelligence that we see in children today: emotional, creative, and instructional. The traditional classroom environment, which typically encourages lecture-based lessons, focuses more on the latter option. Standardized tests and similar ranking tools do the same. When kids have access to technology today, then those who excel outside of the standard learning setup can still achieve their full potential.

- Technology allows students to embrace their curiosity in multiple ways. They can try new things without embarrassment because their tech access gives them a level of anonymity. This process allows students to work, through trial-and error if they wish, to see if a different strategy helps them to learn more effectively.

- Technology allows us to give students access to data from a single location. Do you remember when a research project meant a visit to the library so that you could pull 4-5 books to read, have access to an encyclopedia, and even microfilm to view so that you had enough resources to finish your assignment? Technology allows a student to access every item they need for a project from a central resource. Instead of spending all of that time searching for something specific or waiting for your library to order it, you can run a few queries on Google and find what you need.

- IT and the necessity of changing education Advent of PC (personal computers) and extent access to the internet establishes an environment making global education systems obliged to change their education structure in major ways.⁵ The duty of educational systems confronting the changes is clear. Its primary purpose should be increasing the human power against changes, i.e. someone can adapt to continuous change, observing economy, quickly. The more rapid change, the more attention should be paid to recognizing the pattern of future events. To help humans to remove future shock, we should establish a meta-industrial educational system. For this, instead of searching in the past, we should find our purposes and methods in the future. It is obvious that in 21st century the world will be dominated by modern technology and due to rapid scientific, economic, cultural and political changes, the educational systems will not be able to consider themselves as islands separated from the other social and national organization in the global village.

Because the education, both in the view of historical empiricism and particular conditions encompassing 21st century, surely, will be the center of changes, evolutions and multiplications of 21st century. Certainly the society doesn't view IT only as an economic variable and political lever, but as a possibility for changing education through IT. So one can

suppose proposed patterns of IT in education as center on nature of knowledge, functional techniques and a controlling criterion in society. The advantages of using technology.

1. The presence of technology can be distracting to students. When kids play video games, they can find themselves reacting with addiction-like behaviors. Their focus is on the entertainment they receive more than anything else. If the educational environment uses reward-based games to encourage learning, then the child might be more concerned with what they receive through the software or app instead of what they are learning. Although correct answers can be an indication of knowledge, there might not be as much information retention as hoped. Teachers must set and enforce healthy boundaries when using technology in the classroom to ensure healthy results are possible.

2. Technology can make it easier to cheat. Remember the TV shows and movies where kids would break into a teacher's classroom, steal the answer key to a test, and then write down everything on their wrist, shoe, or a slip of paper? Now a student can send themselves a text with that information. They can send that data to anyone else with a phone. Email can relay this info too. There must also be strict rules in place about the use of technology during quizzes or tests when an exact measurement of student knowledge is needed to evaluate their overall progress.

3. Some technologies could replace the teacher in some classrooms. Interactive learning lessons are so effective today that the software or app can become the teacher instead of having someone present to help a student. One of the best examples of this potential disadvantage is ABC Mouse, which provides clear instructions to students as young as 3 so that they can start learning when they are ready. Instead of being in a hands-on role, technology makes the teacher more of an observer. New tech automates the learning process while adapting to changing student needs.

CONCLUSION . In today's world education needs modern, moderate and simple technologies in order to meet its needs for its arrival and correct use. While there may be varying levels of comfort based on how much access each person has to computers, electronic whiteboards, and other products, introducing new tech is an investment that can produce ongoing dividends.

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